

Semiconductor Die Design with Pre-Applied Die Attach Material

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Keywords— Silicon die; pre-applied filler; laser groove; adhesion; die attach material.

I. OVERVIEW

- Front-of-line (FOL) processes namely the wafer pre-assembly and die attach processes have challenges especially in processing thin dice with thickness ranging from 50µm to 120µm
- Typical assembly manufacturing process flow in Fig. 1 shows the mentioned processes at FOL stations

Fig. 1. Assembly manufacturing process flow.

II. PROBLEM IDENTIFICATION

- Potential die-related issues like die cracks, die delamination, and die attach voids in Fig. 2 occur

especially on thin die applications during diebonding or die attach process

Fig. 2. Die-related anomalies.

- With the increasing demand on thin die applications, mitigation of die-related issues is one big challenge during wafer preparation or pre-assembly and the diebonding process

III. SEMICONDUCTOR DIE DESIGN SOLUTION

- Silicon die backside area is augmented with pre-applied die attach material or filler material on the die's grooved periphery
- With pre-applied filler material, the die attach coverage is enhanced and the die attach adhesion is more robust

The process may follow:

Wafer Taping (Active Side on Tape) → Backside Laser Groove → Wafer Detaping → Filler Mount → Curing → Wafer Mounting (Backside on Tape) → Wafer Sawing

Fig. 3. Semiconductor die augmentation with pre-applied die attach material.

- Laser grooving technology is used for the formation of the peripheral groove
- The semiconductor die design with pre-applied die attach material could help mitigate die to die attach delamination
- Lower coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE) mismatch is created between the pre-applied filler or die attach material and the subsequent die attach material
- With the design, die cracks could be prevented and die attach voids could be minimized